

PROCESS MODELING OF COMPOSITES USING A MULTISCALE FRAMEWORK

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ABSTRACT

Processing of thermoplastic and thermosetting composites is accompanied by the production of residual stresses due to the thermal contraction mismatch between reinforcing fibers and matrix, as well as from curing shrinkage (in thermosets) and crystalline region formation (in thermoplastics). The production of residual stresses in the matrix region result in the compromised laminate strength and structural performance. Multiscale modelling; incorporating molecular dynamics, micromechanics, and finite element simulation; have been used to predict the evolution of residual stresses in both thermoplastic and thermoset composites. This paper outlines some of the efforts to use multiscale modeling to predict the mechanical performance of the resin phase of composites during processing, which is a critical element in predicting the influence of residual stresses on laminate strength.

1 INTRODUCTION

During the processing of high-performance thermoset polymer matrix composites, chemical reactions occur during elevated pressure and temperature cycles, causing the constituent monomers to crosslink and form a molecular network that gradually can sustain stress. As the crosslinking process progresses, the material naturally experiences a gradual shrinkage due to the increase in covalent bonds in the network. Once the cured composite completes the cure cycle and is brought to room temperature, the thermal expansion mismatch of the fibers and matrix cause additional residual stresses to form. These compounded residual stresses can compromise the reliability of the composite material. Therefore, careful material design and processing parameter optimization is necessary.

The crystalline/amorphous phase topology of most thermoplastics is known to evolve kinetically when annealed at elevated temperatures during composite processing. The transformation of the higher-energy amorphous phase to the lower-energy crystalline phase is known to be accompanied by a volumetric shrinkage. Similar to the shrinkage in thermosets, this shrinkage has the potential to cause residual stresses during composite processing because of the presence of a network of stiffer reinforcing inclusions. Excessive residual stresses adversely affect the composite performance and can result in shape deformations in the final composite component.

Composite process modeling is greatly complicated by the multiscale nature of the composite architecture. At the molecular level, the degree of cure (and degree of crystallinity) controls the local shrinkage and thermal-mechanical properties of the thermoset. At the microscopic level, the local fiber architecture and packing affect the magnitudes and locations of residual stress concentrations. At the macroscopic level, the layup sequence controls the nature of crack initiation and propagation due to residual stresses. Recently, a multiscale modeling approach was introduced to relate processing parameters to bulk-level behavior [1-7]. This approach incorporates molecular dynamics (MD) and finite element (FE) simulation to relate molecular-level phenomena to residual stress accumulation during the composite manufacturing process. Although many MD and FE simulation protocols have been established for this method, the full integration of the two modeling schemes must still be achieved.

The goal of this research is to use MD and FE to predict the residual stresses in unidirectional lamina for various thermoset and thermoplastic composite systems. MD is used to predict the polymer shrinkage and thermomechanical properties (elastic, strength, glass transition, thermal expansion) as a function of degree of cure (crystallinity). This information is used as input into FE to predict the residual stresses

on the microscopic level resulting from the complete cure process. Experimental characterization is used to establish cure kinetics and to validate the modeling. This paper provides a summary of some of the latest results of this research effort. The details of the MD and FEA procedures can be found elsewhere [1-7].

2 PEEK PROCESS MODELING

Polyether ether ketone (PEEK) is a high-performance thermoplastic used in many composite material applications requiring toughness levels that thermoset composites typically cannot provide. Kashmari et al [7] built on the work of Pisani et al [8] to establish the properties of PEEK during processing, specifically in the annealing stage in which crystallization occurs. Using MD and micromechanics modelling, the simulated length scales ranged from the nano to the micro levels. Figure 1 shows the MD models utilized for the prediction of properties in the amorphous and crystalline regions of the PEEK microstructure. Figure 2 shows the evolution of the mechanical properties of PEEK during processing, as a result of the crystallization. It is clear that the Young's modulus and shear modulus increase during the anneal. This increase is because of the formation of the stiffer crystalline phase within the material. The Poisson's ratio decreases with annealing time as the material compressibility increases with the complex crystalline micro-structure.

Figure 1: PEEK MD models.

Figure 2: Mechanical properties of PEEK as a function of processing time.

3 PROCESS MODELING OF EPOXY

Epoxy composites are heavily used in the aerospace industry because of their ease of processability, and mechanical integrity for demanding aerospace conditions. In particular, bisphenol-A composites provide an excellent compromise between processability and performance. In order to utilize process modeling for the prediction and reduction of residual stresses, the thermos-mechanical properties need to be determined as a function of degree of cure. Desphande et al [9] utilized MD simulation to predict the properties of bisphenol-A epoxy as a function crosslink density.

Figure 3: (a) DGEBA molecule, (b) D230 ($n = 2$) molecule, (c) D230 ($n = 3$) molecule, and (d) fully densified MD model of EPON 828 – Jeffamine D230.

Figure 3 shows a representative MD model of epoxy in its equilibrated state. The evolution of the clusters during crosslinking is shown in Figure 4. The extent of network formation is defined using the cluster conversion, where in an ideal case the number of clusters at the maximum crosslinking should be one, or 100% networking for the neat resin system. For the uncrosslinked polymer, a total of 456 clusters were present corresponding to the total molecule count before crosslinking. For the maximum crosslinked polymer, the final cluster count was between 1-4 amongst the five replicates. The results indicate that at a crosslink density of 90%, the network was completely linked, and no further chemical reaction occur.

Figure 5 shows the evolution of the mass density as a function of crosslink density, along with experimental data for the fully-cured state [10]. The data clearly shows that the mass density steadily increases between 0 and 50% crosslink density and remains constant thereafter. Comparing with the data in Figure 4, it is evident that the mass density reaches its maximum value before crosslinking is complete. The simulated data also compares favorably with experiment, which is a critical requirement for accurate MD simulation of polymers [11].

Figure 6 shows the volumetric shrinkage of the epoxy during the crosslinking process. Similar to the mass density data, it is evident that the shrinkage is steady until about 50% crosslink density, after which it remains constant. The gel point is shown to be at 50% crosslink density. Thus, the post-gelation shrinkage for this system is small. The calculation of the gel point is shown in Figure 7, where it is evident that around 55% crosslink density the largest cluster starts to rapidly increase in size, the second-largest cluster starts to reduce in size, and the RMW (reduced molecular weight) reaches its maximum value.

Figure 4: Evolution of polymer clusters with progressive crosslinking. (inset) MD models with different clusters at various crosslink densities.

Figure 5: Predicted mass density for different crosslink densities and the reported mass density values from literature [10].

Figure 6: Predicted volume shrinkage at 300 K temperature.

Figure 7: Gel point prediction by tracking molecular mass of fragments where, p-Chain, s-Chain, and RMW represent the largest molecule, second largest molecule, and reduced molecular weight, respectively.

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